

Role of Ecofeminism in Environmental Protection

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Abstract

Environment is the source of all forms and support system of life (UNESCO&ICSU,1999). There are different types of environment comprises physical, cultural, social, economic, intellectual etc. The survival of human and nonhuman creatures depends on the protection of terrestrial eco system and halt biodiversity loss. The environmental protection activities are undertaken by Governments, Writers, NGO's, Political parties, religious institutions and Medias etc. The Earth was called as goddess, which represents a feminine gender implies intimate relationship between Earth and Women. The concept of Mother Goddess is a personification of nature, Motherhood, Fertility, creation, destruction etc. Women, children as well as marginalised sections are the prime victims of natural degradation (Akwa, 2008) . The gender discrimination and suppression of women and nature gave rise to the emergence of ecofeministic theories. The term ecofeminism is used to describe a feministic approach to understanding ecology. Ecofeminist literature is a recent origin in Kerala but several authors and women activists follows its path years ago. Sugathakumari, Balamaniyamma, Sara Joseph, P. Valsala, C.K Janu, Mayilamma, ect contributed more in this field. This study is an attempt to examining the role of ecofeminism in environmental protection.

Keywords: NGO's, Ecofeminism, Terrestrial ecosystem, Mother Goddess, Marginalised sections.

Objectives of the Study

1. To analyse the history of ecofeminism
2. To examine the role of ecofeminism in environmental protection
3. To review ecofeministic literature in Malayalam.

Methodology

Secondary sources like books, articles, magazines, internet sources etc are used to gather information's regarding ecofeministic ideologies and its implications in environmental protection.

Introduction

"Ecology" is a biological science which deals with complex interactions among organisms and their environment. The habits of animals and plants in different areas are described in the writings of Hippocrates, Aristotle, Theophratus, Reaumer etc. The word feminism implies the equality of men and women. Feminism is a range of movements that share's a common goal to achieve personal, political, economic and social equality of sexes. Ecofeminism is a blending of ecology and feminism. The term ecofeminism was coined by French writer Francois Eaubonne in1974. Ecofeminism emerged in the western countries as a result of the ecological and feministic movements of 1970s and 1980s. "Ecofeminism is about connectedness and wholeness of theory and practice.....(it sees)the devastation of earth and her beings

by the corporate warriors and the threat of nuclear annihilation by the military warriors. It is the same masculinist mentality which would deny us our right to our own bodies and our own sexuality and which depends on multiple systems of dominance and state power to have its way” (Ynestra king).

In 1970 ecofeminism gave its birth in France, Germany, Japan, Finland, Australia etc. The developers of ecofeministic ideas like Susan Griffin, Mary Daly, Carolyn Merchant, Ynestra King, Ariel Kay Salleh, Val Plumwood and others emphasise that ecological issues are the basic issues of women's, because there is always a correlation between oppression of women's and oppression of nature. Therefore we can analyse that there exists an ecological perspective in feminist theories.

Nature and women are exploited in the same way, if these two are not protected and preserved, there is no existence for world environment (ecofeminism As politics, nature, Marx and the post modern - Ariel Salleh). The feminist ideology has its own path of development, it starts from liberal feminism and proceeds to Radical feminism, from there it enriched through social feminism and finally reached the stage of ecofeminism.

Ecofeministic ideology propagates women as a centre of resistance against all types of exploitations. Rachel Carson's epic 'silent spring' represents such a resistance. It created a revolutionary change in the attitude of administrative authorities on environment. Ecofeminism accepts all merits of liberal, Radical and social feminist ideas. Ariel Salleh presents an interesting example of capitalistic exploitative interests. That is, if we regularise our world into a village, and assume there are only 100 human beings, then they consist of 57 Asians, 21 Europeans, 14 Americans and the rest of them will be Africans. If we analyse their colour 30 will be white toned ones and remaining 70 will be in other colours. If we analyse their religion, 30 should be Christians and 70 should be non-Christians. If we analyse their economic background, only 6 acquire the 50% of world property and they surely be Americans. Among 100's 70 should be illiterates and undernourished. It depicts the horrible state of injustice and inequality among human beings. Ecofeministic thinkers are continuously encountering these realities where others are retrieving..

Ecofeminism in India

The ecofeministic thinker's establishes the relationship between women and nature through popularising the ancient worshipping concept of Mothergoddess. Woman's have an intimate relationship with nature. She knows everything about nature therefore she uses natural resources efficiently and economically.

Vandana Shiva, the pioneer of ecofeministic ideas in India advocates that the close relationship between women and nature help her to understand the impulse of nature in its depth. According to Vandana Shiva "Liberation is best to begin the colonised and end with the coloniser". The development of Eurocentric masculinity as a part of capitalistic thinking aimed to exploit natural resources, and marginalised communities including women's. Therefore as a liberation movement ecofeminism needed to resist all types of exploitations. Some major environmental movements for protecting the interest of environment and marginalised sections includes- Bishnoi movement, Chipko movement, Narmada Bacho Andolan, Appiko movement, Silent valley movement, Navdanya movement, Save Chaliyar movement, Plachimada struggle, Muthanga struggle etc.

Bishnoi movement: This protest was undertaken by a nonviolent community of nature worshippers of Rajasthan known as Bishnois under the leadership of a sage Sombaji against deforestation.

Chipko movement: The chipko movement in Utharanjal is a tree-hugging campaign to resist tree cutting headed by noted environmentalist Sunderlal Bahuguna in 1970 in order to safeguard the biodiversity of Himalayan Range.

Narmada Bachao Andolan: This movement protested against Narmada River Valley project in order to preserve the interest of minorities under the leadership of Medha Patkar and Baba Amtey.

Appiko movement: This movement is started in Karnataka as a forest conservation movement against governmental intervention in to forest for monoculture teak and eucalyptus plantations.

Navdanya movement: It is a NGO established by Vandana Shiva for biodiversity conservation through setting up of 54 community seed banks. 'Diverse women for Diversity' is their global campaign for food security and biodiversity.

Silent valley movement: It is a movement to protect Silent Valley (an evergreen tropical forest in Palakkad district of Kerala) in 1973 against Kundramukku project in Kunthippuza River.

Salu marada movement: In Karnataka a leading environmental movement in Karnataka state was undertaken by Thimmakka. Her life depicts the intimate relationship between women and nature. She along with her husband planted 8000 trees within 65 years.

Muthanga struggle: This struggle was undertaken by the leadership of CK Janu in wayanad district for conserving the rights of Adivasis.

Plachimada struggle: This protest was undertaken to preserve environmental sustainability of Plachimada village of Palakkad against Coca Cola factory under the leadership of Mayilamma.

Ecofeminism in Malayalam Literature

The ecofeministic ideology reached in Kerala recently. Therefore it is considered as an unexploded area for Malayalees. Even though there are certain writer's who tried to integrate feministic ideologies with nature. Through their workings they tried to create strong ecological insight in readers. They includes:

Kamala Das: Kamala Das absorbed the characteristics of modernism, post modernism, feminism and environmentalism in her writings. But her works are not in an apt reflection of western ecofeminism. The changing morals, perceptions and attitudes of society are accurately portrayed in her works. She is a guiding personality for the new generation poets like, V.M Girija, Prameela Devi, Kanimol, Sushama, Geetha Hiranyan etc.

Lalithambika Antharjanam: The different perspectives of ecofeministic ideologies are more demanded in the works of Lalithambika Antharjanam.

Sarajoseph: Through her workings Sara Joseph revealed the apathetic situations of women's in a heart touching style. She is also a founder of 'MANUSHI' (The organisation of thinking women)

P.Valsala: The short stories and novels of valsala depicted women's character with strong determination and deep ecological impact.

Conclusion

Ecofeminism is a movement for existence of life. It is considered as a revolutionary movement for the liberation of women, men and nature. It introduces a new equation for life, that is : Man/Women = Nature. It is always the marginalised sections like wemons, tribals, peasants etc are the real victims of capitalistic exploitations and environmental degradation. Hence they are the most active in the protest against these... Therefore the survival of ecofeministic ideology lies in a socio economic system which promotes equality, justice, non violence, cultural values etc.

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